

Coating thickness in welded joints and its effect on detectability by magnetic particle testing

Jorge Vera Alvarado¹; Luis Caballero García²; Martin Taboada Neira³; Luis Aguilar Rodríguez⁴; Luis Vega Alcántara⁵; Jhon Velásquez Maldonado⁶
Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, Perú

Magnetic particle nondestructive testing is widely used to evaluate defects in welded structures and components and to ensure their reliability and functionality. As they are often subjected to surface coating processes to extend their service life, there is uncertainty in the detection of these defects, so it was proposed to determine the effect of coating thickness size on the ability of magnetic particle testing to reveal defects in welded joints. Tests were performed on welded specimens containing surface defects and coated at three thickness levels. The estimation of the detection capability of the tests was performed by the POD Hit/miss statistical method using the mh1823POD program, obtaining the probability of detection curves for each thickness level. The results showed that as the coating thickness increases, the detection rate and capacity decrease; the magnetic particle inspection presents a better performance in samples with an average thickness of 73 μm , detecting defects greater than or equal to 14.15 with a high probability.

Keywords: Coating thickness, Welded joints, Detection capacity, Magnetic particles.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15880723

¹ M.Sc. in Materials Science and Technology and Ph.D. in Environmental Sciences. Contact: jvera@unitru.edu.pe

² Metallurgical Engineer and Master in Engineering. Contact: lcaballero@unitru.edu.pe

³ Metallurgical Engineer and PhD in Environmental Sciences. Contact: mtaboada@unitru.edu.pe

⁴ Metallurgical Engineer and PhD in Materials Science and Technology. Contact: laguilar@unitru.edu.pe

⁵ Metallurgical Engineer. Contact: jvega@unitru.edu.pe

⁶ Metallurgical Engineer. Contact: jvelasquezmal@unitru.edu.pe

1. INTRODUCTION

Periodic inspection of structures and components in service has become an essential aspect in several industries, to guarantee safety and functional conditions. Among the inspection methods, nondestructive testing (NDT) is widely employed as it enables timely detection and evaluation of defects without causing damage to the material under inspection [1-4].

In industries such as construction, marine, and oil, it is necessary to ensure the quality and durability of metal structures and components; therefore, it is common to apply protective coatings to prevent corrosion and wear losses in critical areas, such as welds.

However, the application of these coatings can lead to difficulties when inspecting the welded joints. In such cases, one of the NDT methods that can be employed is nondestructive testing with magnetic particles, which can detect surface defects in the weld zones that have been coated [5-7].

Magnetic particle testing involves the induction of a magnetizing force on a ferromagnetic material, generating a magnetic field. When surface defects are present perpendicular to the lines of force, magnetic flux leakage occurs, which attracts the magnetic particles applied during the test, resulting in the formation of indications that reveal the defects present [8, 9].

The evaluation of nondestructive testing capability is important for the selection of the most appropriate technique in a specific application, this evaluation is carried out by determining the probability of detection (POD), which represents the probability of identifying a defect about its size by a nondestructive testing method [9-12].

Studies on the capability of nondestructive testing on welded structures indicate that this methodology provides a quantification of the detection capability of various methods, such as ultrasonic testing [13], liquid penetrant [14, 15, 16], and magnetic particle [17, 18].

POD finds fundamental applications in the design, manufacture, and maintenance of structures, equipment, and components, the development of inspection procedures, and the evaluation of inspectors' performance [9, 19].

The probability of detection is calculated from results obtained in nondestructive tests, using the statistical methods $POD \hat{a}$ vs a , if the results are quantitative and POD Hit/miss, when they are qualitative. The graphical representation of the POD consists of a probability curve, which relates defect sizes to the probability of being detected [11, 19, 20].

To ensure the integrity of a welded product, it is essential that magnetic particle testing identifies any defects that could lead to potential future failures. However, when the elements to be inspected have some type of coating, the effectiveness of the tests to detect possible damage can be affected.

For this reason, an investigation has been considered to evaluate the effect of coating thickness on the ability to detect defects in welded joints using magnetic particle testing.

2. METHOD

2.1 Object of study

Twenty carbon steel samples welded in groove and fillet, butt joint, and T-joint were used, shown in Figure 1.

The samples were examined with a digital stereoscope, finding a total of 60 surface defects, a sufficient number to form the data set for the estimation of the probability of detection by the POD Hit/miss method.

Figure 1. Welded samples for study

2.2 Procedure

2.2.1 Application of anti-rust paint coating

The surfaces of the samples were pre-cleaned by mechanical and chemical methods to remove oxides, dirt, grease, incrustations, or other materials that could hinder the application of the paint.

Rust-Oleum cold galvanized composite spray paint coating was applied over the entire weld bead and within 3 cm on each side of the bead. Two successive coats of paint were applied making sure to achieve uniform coverage, with a 15-minute break between the application of each coat, followed by a drying period at room temperature for 24 hours.

2.2.2 Measuring the thickness of rustproofing paint coating

Verification of the coating thickness, in micrometers, was performed using the Positector 6000 DeFelsko portable gauge, which uses secondary current principles to measure thicknesses. Measurements were taken at five different points within the painted area on the welded samples to obtain an average value.

2.2.3 Inspection of rustproof paint-coated specimens by magnetic particle tests

Magnetic particle inspections were carried out according to the test procedure developed under the reference standards ASME Section V Article 7 [21] and ASTM E 709 [22].

The magnetization of the surface of each welded sample was performed with a Y-7 Magnaflux electromagnetic yoke using direct current: subsequently, Magnavis 8A red magnetic particles were added by dry spraying with a hand-held bulb over the entire painted area. The welded samples were examined under white light, and the indications detected in each sample were measured with a vernier caliper and recorded photographically for later analysis.

Figure 2 presents a block diagram that summarizes the experimental procedure carried out in the investigation. Three paint applications were performed on the welded samples to obtain three levels of coating thickness. Between each application, thickness measurements and magnetic particle inspections were performed.

Figure 2. Experimental procedure

2.3 Statistical Analysis

The analysis of the magnetic particle test results was carried out using the POD Hit/Miss statistical method. In this method, a value of 1 is assigned to the data corresponding to defects detected (Hit) and a value of 0 to those not detected (miss). The generation of the POD curve is based on the use of generalized linear models (GLM) and a specific link function, which can be the logit, probit, cloglog, or loglog function. In addition, a maximum likelihood fit to the data is employed to estimate the model parameters and obtain the shape of the curve [11, 20]. Equation (1) describes the POD as a function of defect size.

$$POD(a) = \frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \log(a))}{1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \log(a))} \quad (1)$$

Where $POD(a)$ is the probability of detection for a , a is the dimension of the defect, β_0 y β_1 1 parameters of the model [11].

In the present investigation, the mh1823POD program available online [20] was used to perform the statistical analysis using the POD Hit/miss method described and thus plot the POD curves for each thickness level.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Coating thickness measurements

The thickness levels of the coating applied on the welded specimens were verified using Posi Tector 6000 electronic equipment, as illustrated in Figure 3. Measurements were taken at five different points within the painted area and averaged. The average thicknesses of the applied coatings are 73 μm for the first level of thickness, 163 μm for the second level, and 271 μm for the third level.

Figure 3. Measurement of coating thickness on sample

3.2 Defects detected by magnetic particles

Table 1 details the total number of detected and undetected defects in the study samples. For each coating thickness level, the corresponding detection rates were calculated from the total of 60 defects previously examined in the uncoated samples, showing a decrease in the detection rate as the thickness increases.

Table 1. The detection rate of magnetic particle tests.

Thickness level (μm)	Number of defects detected	Number of undetected defects	Detection rate (%)
73	45	18	71,43
163	40	23	63,49
271	33	30	52,38

3.3 POD detection probability curves

The POD curves of the tests performed with magnetic particles are shown in Figures 4, 5, and 6, for an average thickness level of $73\mu\text{m}$, $163\mu\text{m}$, and $271\mu\text{m}$ respectively.

Figure 4. POD curve in samples with an average thickness of $73\mu\text{m}$

Figure 5. POD curve for samples with an average thickness of $163\mu\text{m}$

Figure 6. POD curve in samples with an average thickness of 271 μm

Table 2 details the values of a_{50} y a_{90} values for each coating thickness level, obtained from the POD curves of the magnetic particle tests on the welded samples.

Table 2. Detected size values for magnetic particle tests

Thickness level (μm)	a_{50} (mm)	a_{90} (mm)
73	2,682	14,15
163	3,938	22,45
271	6,101	56,87

The results show that the coating thickness influences the magnetic particle testing capability; having a higher detection rate at a lower level of thickness. In addition, it is observed that the value of a_{90} , which represents the detectable defect size with 90% probability, differs in each curve, being 14.15 mm for an average thickness of 73 μm, 22.45 mm for the thickness of 163 μm, and 56.87 mm for a thickness of 271 μm; this indicates that, as the thickness increases, the defects most likely to be detected will be those of larger size, while those of smaller size, which are usually the most critical, are less likely to be detected; inferring that the magnetic particle test will be less effective on welded specimens having a high coating thickness.

The coating applied on parts by painting, plating, or other techniques can hide surface defects, making them difficult to detect or causing them to be missed completely by generating somewhat blurred indications during magnetic particle testing. In addition, it is possible for a very hard coating to crack while the base metal remains intact, generating non-relevant indications that confuse inspection [9].

Some specifications limit the paint thickness to 0.003 in (0.076 mm), requiring the removal of the paint when this limit is exceeded, because it can affect the sensitivity of the magnetic particle tests [9]. The results of the present study evidenced that the magnetic particle test has the highest detection capacity for the average thickness of 73 μm (0.073 mm), decreasing its capacity when the thicknesses are 163 μm (0.163 mm) and 271 μm (0.271 mm).

4. CONCLUSIONS

The performance of nondestructive magnetic particle testing using an electromagnetic yoke is significantly affected by the thickness of the coating applied on the welded specimens. As the thickness increases, the flaw detection rate decreases from 71.43% for an average thickness of 73 μm to 52.38% for a thickness of 271 μm.

In addition, at a lower thickness level, the magnetic particle test presents higher detection capability, allowing it to detect defects larger than 14.15 mm with a high probability for 73 μm thickness, and decreasing its efficiency as thicknesses increase to 163 μm and 271 μm .

Future research may consider other magnetization techniques, or explore coating alternatives, which could improve the prospects for the ability to identify defects by testing magnetic particles in coated solder joints.

REFERENCES

- [1] Smith R. (2015). Non-destructive testing (NDT) - Guidance document: an Introduction to NDT common methods. The British Institute of Non-Destructive Testing.
- [2] Cawley E. (2001). Non-destructive- testing - current capabilities and future directions. Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part L: Journal of Materials: Design and Applications 215(4), 213-223.
- [3] Ashok K. (2017). Non-Destructive Testing, Evaluation of Stainless-Steel Materials. Materials Today Proceedings 4(8), 7302-7312.
- [4] Deepak J. et al. (2021). Non-destructive testing (NDT) techniques for low carbon steel welded joints: A review and experimental study. Materials Today Proceedings 44, 3732-3737.
- [5] Votava J. (2013). Protection of welded joints against corrosion degradation. Acta Univ. Agric. Silvic. Mendel. Brun. 61(6), 1897-1904.
- [6] Hashimoto K. et al. (2006). Research On Development of a Non-destructive Crack Inspection System by Using Magnetic Properties. In The Sixteenth International Offshore and Polar Engineering Conference. San Francisco, California.
- [7] Cao R. (2017). Research progress on corrosion and protection of welded joints of pipeline steels. Corrosion Science and Protection Technology 29(6), 657-663.
- [8] Eisenmann D. (2014). Review of progress in magnetic particle inspection. AIP Conference Proceedings, 1581, 1505-1510.
- [9] American Society for Nondestructive Testing. (2013). ASNT Level III Study Guide: Magnetic Particle Testing Method Second Edition. ASNT.
- [10] Keprate A. (2016). Probability of detection: History, development, and future. Pipeline Technology Journal 8, 41-45.
- [11] U.S. Department of Defense. (2009). Nondestructive evaluation system reliability assessment. MIL-HDBK-1823A, USA.
- [12] Yee B. et al. (1976). Assessment of NDE Reliability Data. Report NASA CR-134991, USA.
- [13] Kurz J. (2012). Probability of detection (POD) determination using ultrasound phased array for considering NDT in probabilistic damage assessments. En 18th World Conference on Non-Destructive Testing. South Africa.
- [14] Zolfaghari A. y Kolahan F. (2017). Reliability and sensitivity of visible liquid penetrant NDT for inspection of welded components. Materials Testing 59(3), 290-294.
- [15] Fonseca R. et al. (2014). Study of probability of the detection of defects in welded joints of the techniques of magnetic particle and penetrant testing. En 13th International Symposium on Nondestructive Characterization of Materials (NDCM-XIII). Le Mans, Francia.
- [16] Vera J. (2023). Capacidad del Método de Líquidos Penetrantes para Detectar Defectos en Soldadura. En 21st LACCEI International Multi-Conference for Engineering, Education, and Technology. Buenos Aires, Argentina.
- [17] Zolfaghari A. et al. (2018). Reliability and sensitivity of magnetic particle nondestructive testing in detecting the surface cracks of welded components. Nondestructive Testing and Evaluation 33(3), 290-300.
- [18] Vera J. et al. (2022). Capacidad de detección de defectos en juntas soldadas al variar la técnica de ensayo con partículas magnéticas. En Multiconferencia Internacional HUMANOS-XXI. Antioquía, Colombia.
- [19] Virkkunen I. et al. (2019). Comparison of \hat{a} versus a and hit/miss POD-Estimation Methods: A European viewpoint. Journal of Nondestructive Evaluation 38(89), 1-13.
- [20] Charles A. (2022). Statistical best-practices for building probability of detection (POD) models. R package mh1823 POD, version 5.4.5. En <https://statistical-engineering.com/>, accessed 10 Diciembre 2022.
- [21] American Society of Mechanical Engineers. (2021). ASME BPVC Section V Nondestructive Examination. ASME.
- [22] American Society for Testing and Materials. (2021). ASTM E709: Standard Guide for Magnetic Particle Testing. ASTM.